

Trusting *forward*

10 **Health-RI**
OCT **CONFERENCE**
24

Leveraging different types of molecular data to understand health and disease *(in English)*

The role of data infrastructure in multi-omics research

**Prof. dr. Bauke
Ylstra**

Chair
Amsterdam
UMC

**Prof. dr.
Peter-Bram
't Hoen**

*X-omics -
Radboudumc*

**Dr. Magnus
Palmblad**

*Proteomics –
LUMC*

**Prof. dr. Lisenka
Vissers**

*Genomics –
Radboudumc*

**Dr. Denise
Slenter**

*Metabolomics –
Maastricht University*

Schedule (13:30-14:30)

- Setting the scene (Bauke Ylstra)
- Multi-omics research use cases
 - Proteomics - Magnus Palmblad
 - Genomics - Lisenka Vissers
 - Multi-omics data integration with the FAIR Data Cube - Peter-Bram 't Hoen
 - Metabolomics - Denise Slenters
- Slido
 - Collect input/questions from audience
- Panel discussion (chair Bauke Ylstra)
 - The role of data infrastructure in multi-omics research

Setting the scene

- Omics data is becoming very prominent in the study and diagnosis of very diverse diseases, from rare diseases to cancer, and they are important for the understanding of common diseases but also for personalizing treatments.
- Different types of molecular data look at different types of molecules of life and combining these is the holy grail for understanding the biology of life and health.
- In this session we want to hear the motivation for sharing molecular data from our experts and engage panel members as well as the audience in discussions about the technical and social barriers that need to be cleared by and through Health-RI to make it work.

Setting the scene

- The premise: understanding biology is fundamental to understanding health and multi-omics research is needed to understand biology.
- The Health-RI connection: We need services like metadata agreements, catalogues, and secure processing environments to find, access and re-use multi-omics data in a safe way.
- Building the story: How is Health-RI infrastructure going to advance your research and contribute to the understanding of the molecular processes in life?

Bring in your points!

- Go to www.slido.com
- Enter the code 202 66 16
- Enter your thoughts, questions, remarks for the panel discussion
- Vote for the discussion points that you find most relevant

TGAC Introduction

The Tumor Genome Analysis Core Pricing

The Tumor Genome Analysis Core

- Primary goal: ***Impact for patients***

TGAC Operation

Sample Collection

Sample Processing

Sequence Reads

Processed Data

Data Availability

This section highlights data availability through a collage of scientific publications and logos. At the top left is the 'HemaSphere' logo. Below it is a paper titled 'Genetic and Microenvironment Features Do Not Distinguish Follicular Lymphoma Patients Requiring Immediate or Deferred Treatment' by Thomas F. Eleveld, Chaima Bakali, Paul P. Eijk, Phylis Stathi, Lianne E. Vriend, Pino J. Poddaghe, and Bauke Ylstra. To the right is a 'NAR Breakthrough Article' titled 'Engineering large-scale chromosomal deletions by CRISPR-Cas9' by the same authors. Below these is the 'JOURNAL OF CLINICAL ONCOLOGY' logo. In the center is a paper titled 'Genomic landscape of metastatic colorectal cancer' by Josep C. Hain, Maritza Labas, Christian Basso, Miriam Escamez, Jochen Sp, Vanita JM, Makarewicz, Mark A. van de Worp, Daniele Vanni, Hendrik J. van Erven, Nicole C.T. van Gool, Quimich Ah, van der, Mark W. Boer, Susana Q, Onir Kabanov, Joke M.W. van der, and D. Nagtegaal, Corrado J.A. Punt, Bauke Ylstra, and Gerrit A. Meijer. To the right is another paper titled 'Loss of Chromosome 18q11.2-q12.1 Is Predictive for Survival in Patients With Metastatic Colorectal Cancer Treated With Bevacizumab' by the same authors. At the bottom right is a text box: 'The path towards consensus genome classification of diffuse large B-cell lymphoma for use in clinical practice' by Matias Mendeville, Margaretha G. M. Roemer, G. Tijlke Los-de Vries, Martine E. D. Chamuleau, and Daphne de Jong and Bauke Ylstra. At the bottom are logos for 'GEO Gene Expression Omnibus' and 'EUROPEAN GENOME-PHENOME ARCHIVE'.

GEO
Gene Expression Omnibus
Processed Public Data

EUROPEAN GENOME-PHENOME ARCHIVE
Raw Public Data

GEN-BioDORA

ADORE

Bauke Ylstra
(PI)

Henne Holstege

Yongsoo Kim

Daoud Sie

WO
Leaders

HPC Engineer

Santiago Bolaños M.

Ferdinand v. d. Toorn

Currently
involved

Introduction to the Panelists

1. ***Proteomics*** - *Dr. Magnus Palmblad, Associate professor/group leader bioinformatics, LUMC*
2. ***Genomics*** - *Prof. Dr. Lisenka Vissers, professor of Translational Genomics, Radboudumc*
3. ***X-omics*** - *Prof. Dr. Peter-Bram 't Hoen, Chair of Bioinformatics, Radboudumc*
4. ***Metabolomics*** - *Dr. Denise Slenter, postdoc bioinformatics; board member of NMC Maastricht University*

Proteomics

Magnus Palmblad

Center for Proteomics and Metabolomics

Journal of Proteome Research

Leiden University Medical Center

ELIXIR

Proteomics: How Can We Trust Proteomics Data?

- *Quality control*
- *Openness*
- *Standards*
- *Metadata*

Quality Control

- *QC is required to trust that reported data accurately represents what is in the samples*
 - *Trust in instrument performance*
 - *Trust in peptide and protein identifications, including*
 - *Peptide-spectrum matches*
 - *Peptide identifications*
 - *Protein inferences*
 - *Post-translational localizations*
 - *Trust in quantitative measurements*

Quality Control

- *QC is required to trust that reported data accurately represents what is in the samples*
 - *Trust in instrument performance* ← *QC samples*
 - *Trust in peptide and protein identifications, including*
 - *Peptide-spectrum matches*
 - *Peptide identifications*
 - *Protein inferences* ← *statistics (FDR control)*
 - *Post-translational localizations*
 - *Trust in quantitative measurements*

Openness: PRIDE Repository

- *Quality control metrics*
- *Part of ProteomeXchange consortium*
- *Archives all types of proteomics mass spectrometry*
- *Recently added PRIDE-Controlled Access (PRIDE-CA) for sensitive data*
- *Now being extended to non-MS data (Olink, SomaLogic)*
- *Based on standards*

Standards: Proteomics Standards Initiative

Standards: Proteomics Standards Initiative

Metadata

- *No experimental data is trustable, reproducible or reusable at scale if*
 - *There is no metadata*
 - *The metadata is incomplete*
 - *The metadata is wrong*
 - *The metadata is not machine-actionable*
- *The good news: standard formats, CVs, bespoke tooling and pipeline integration*

Brief Communication

<https://doi.org/10.1038/s41592-024-02343-1>

quantms: a cloud-based pipeline for quantitative proteomics enables the reanalysis of public proteomics data

Received: 12 May 2023

Accepted: 3 June 2024

Published online: 4 July 2024

 Check for updates

Chengxin Dai^{1,2,10}, Julianus Pfeuffer^{3,10}, Hong Wang¹, Ping Zheng¹, Lukas Käll⁴, Timo Sachsenberg^{5,6}, Vadim Demichev⁷, Mingze Bai^{1,2}, Oliver Kohlbacher^{5,6,8} & Yasset Perez-Riverol⁹✉

The volume of public proteomics data is rapidly increasing, causing a computational challenge for large-scale reanalysis. Here, we introduce quantms (<https://quant.ms.org/>), an open-source cloud-based pipeline for massively parallel proteomics data analysis. We used quantms to reanalyze 83 public ProteomeXchange datasets, comprising 29,354 instrument files from 13,132 human samples, to quantify 16,599 proteins based on 1.03 million unique peptides. quantms is based on standard file formats improving the reproducibility, submission and dissemination of the data to ProteomeXchange.

Dai et al. 2024

Dai et al. 2024

Dai et al. 2024

Metadata: The Challenge

- *We must do more to help researchers provide correct, complete and machine-actionable metadata*

Genomics

Lisenka Vissers

Professor of Translational Genomics
Head Genome Research - dpt of Human Genetics

National

International

Radboudumc

Biobank 'Genetics and Rare Disease': >2,000 biomaterials
Nijmegen Phenotypic Database: >9,000 RD patients with clinical data (HPO)
Clinical Utility of novel OMICs for fast translation into routine diagnostics

Primary focus on Genomics for Rare Diseases

THERE ARE AT LEAST
7,000
RARE DISEASES

1 in 17 individuals will be affected by a rare disease throughout their lifetime.

Average of 6 years
For 1 in 5 patients >20 years

75% of rare disease manifests during childhood

80% of diseases is caused by a genetic defect.

30

% of children affect by a rare disease will die from the disorder by the age of 5 years.

1 in 3 patients first receives a wrong diagnosis.

Many different specialisms.
For 1 in 12 patients: >10

2/3 of patients remain without a genetic diagnosis.

Rare disease clinical research leads to new diagnoses and impacts patient & family lives!

6,004 RD families*

New genetic diagnoses

(limited to (likely) pathogenic variants in known disease-gene associations)

*Currently: >27K individuals, >100M unique variants

Challenges: closing the gaps and creating trust!

TRUST & CONTROL

Multi-omics data integration using the FAIR Data Cube

Peter-Bram 't Hoen, Professor of Bioinformatics and FAIR data infrastructure
Department of Medical BioSciences

Radboudumc

FAIR Data Cube explained

Firdaws Badmus, XiaoFeng Liao

Radboudumc

Multi-omics Analysis with FAIR Data Cube

Mapping a SARS-CoV-2 pathway to multi-omics data from FAIR Data Cube

Radboudumc
university medical center

Challenges in Integrated Multi-omics Data Analysis

Data preparation is time and energy consuming

Sensitive data

How can the FAIR Data Cube help?

Multi-omics Workflow

Result

Result

Result

Integration Demonstrated

FDC increases efficiency

Links

- <https://www.x-omics.nl/>
- <https://github.com/Xomics/FAIRDataCube/wiki>
- <https://sparql.wikipathways.org/>
- <https://webservice.bridgedb.org/>
- <https://docs.vantage6.ai/en/main/>

Acknowledgements

- <https://doi.org/10.1101/2023.04.23.23289000>

FAIR Data Cube, a FAIR data infrastructure for
integrated multi-omics data analysis

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K. Joeri van der Velde⁴, Morris A. Swertz⁴, Martin Brandt⁵,
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Challenges

- Creating FAIR (meta)data requires effort: more tooling needed
 - Working with Jasper Koeorst et al. (Wageningen) on FAIR Data Station
- Reuse of other people's data should become more commonplace
 - Recognition and Reward of OpenScience
- Business models around data are lacking
 - Role for data brokers

Denise Slenter

ORCID:0000-0001-8449-1318

Our tools are quite diverse:

BridgeDb

Our tools are quite diverse:

Extending inherited metabolic disorder diagnostics with biomarker interaction visualizations

[Denise Slenter](#), Irene Hemel, Chris Evelo, Jürgen Bierau, Egon Willighagen, Laura Steinbusch

Orphanet Journal of Rare Diseases 18.1 (2023): 95.

DOI:

[10.1186/s13023-023-02683-9](https://doi.org/10.1186/s13023-023-02683-9)

Data and scripts:

github.com/BiGCAT-UM/IMD-PUPY

Website:

bigcat-um.github.io/IMD-PUPY

We designed a novel workflow to support diagnosis

Data integration issues at each level of the workflow

Clinical Biomarker Data

1

Patient data:

- 20 Patients: 5 pyrimidine, 11 urea cycle, 4 dropped.
- Anonymized, labeled A - T
- Two targeted chemical assays in urine ($\mu\text{mol}/\text{mmol}$ creatinine)
- Pyrimidine: PUPY; urea cycle: AA
- 4 patients dropped (labeled B, C, P, and Q), no AA panel

Reference data: \rightarrow n-carbamoyl-aspartate, allantoin, cytosine, cytidine missing

- 4853 samples PUPY (10 y)
- 1872 samples AA (5 y)
- Age ranges: 0-1 y, 1-5 y, 5-16 y, 16y+
- Annotation with ChEBI IDs [14] \rightarrow manual
- or Wikidata [15] \rightarrow 2,8-dihydroxyadenine

[14] Hastings, Nucleic acids research (2016).

[15] Waagmeester, eLife (2020).

[16] Kutmon, PLoS Comput. Biol. (2015).

[17] UniProt Consortium. Nucleic Acids Res. (2021).

[18] Lombardot, Nucleic Acids Res. (2019).

[19] McKusick, JHU Press (1998).

[20] Martens, Nucleic Acids Res. (2021).

[21] Waagmeester, PLoS Comput. Biol. (2016).

[22] Wishart, Nucleic Acids Res. (2018).

[23] van Iersel, BMC bioinformatics (2010).

[24] Heller, J. Cheminform. (2015).

[25] Lee, Genet. Med. (2018).

[26] Tweedie, Nucleic Acids Res. (2021).

[27] Shannon, Genome Res. (2003).

[28] Otasek, Genome Biol. (2019).

[29] Kutmon, F1000Research (2014).

Data integration issues at each level of the workflow

Pathway
Models

2

PathVisio [16]: → **curation info not structured**

- Purine, pyrimidine, urea cycle & 2 biomarker models → **several biomarkers still missing**

Annotations:

- Proteins: UniProt [17] → **isoforms**
- Interactions: Rhea [18] → **diff. in protonation states**
- Metabolites: ChEBI [14] → **mappings to HMDB [22] and back**
- Disorders: OMIM [19] → **merges info on gene level**

Distribution:

- WikiPathways [20] (GPML, GMT, Wikidata [15],)
- SPARQL endpoint RDF [21] → **missing protein groups**

[14] Hastings, Nucleic acids research (2016).

[15] Waagmeester, eLife (2020).

[16] Kutmon, PLoS Comput. Biol. (2015).

[17] UniProt Consortium. Nucleic Acids Res. (2021).

[18] Lombardot, Nucleic Acids Res. (2019).

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[27] Shannon, Genome Res. (2003).

[28] Otasek, Genome Biol. (2019).

[29] Kutmon, F1000Research (2014). 4

Data integration issues at each level of the workflow

ID mapping → manual
BridgeDb [23]

Data transformation → low abundance

Total of 83 markers → seven not in PWM
Converted to neutral InChIKey [24] or substructure
matching

[14] Hastings, Nucleic acids research (2016).
[15] Waagmeester, eLife (2020).
[16] Kutmon, PLoS Comput. Biol. (2015).
[17] UniProt Consortium. Nucleic Acids Res. (2021).

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[29] Kutmon, F1000Research (2014).

Data integration issues at each level of the workflow

Theoretical Biomarker Data

4

IEMbase [25] → no machine-readable download

- Disorders based on HGNC gene name [26] → Not always present
- Sample matrix → PUPY/AA only in urine
- Biomarkers with HMDB IDs [22] → old and new structure
- Age category: 0-1mth, 1-18mths, 1.5-11y, 11-16y, 16y +

Biomarker change

- relative (↑↑↑ vs ↓↓↓) → link to actual data? No refs.

[14] Hastings, Nucleic acids research (2016).

[15] Waagmeester, eLife (2020).

[16] Kutmon, PLoS Comput. Biol. (2015).

[17] UniProt Consortium. Nucleic Acids Res. (2021).

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Biomarker overlap for three IMD types, age category: 0 to 1 years for patient: I

Biomarkers overlap visualization.
Data shown for Patient I.

For the following IMDs, no data was available: TPMT, PRPPS, TYMP, TK2, RRM2B, ITPA, IMPDH1, DHODH, AMPD1.

Data integration issues at each level of the workflow

Cytoscape [27]

- Automated [28]
- WikiPathways App [29]
- Mapping to unified ChEBI [14]

- Interaction IDs (Rhea [18]) missing
- Reactome not possible
- what if no mapping?

Select top 3 relevant PWMs [21]

→ what is “relevant”?

Expert is needed → needs to be trained

[14] Hastings, Nucleic acids research (2016).
[15] Waagmeester, eLife (2020).
[16] Kutmon, PLoS Comput. Biol. (2015).
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[29] Kutmon, F1000Research (2014).

Data Interpretation: easy diagnosis

Network visualization of biomarkers for patient I (diagnosed with DPYD). Left: selected section of pyrimidine biomarkers pathway; Right: selection of purine metabolism pathway.

Data Interpretation: difficult diagnosis

Biomarker overlap for three IMD types,
age category: 1 to 5 years
for patient:G

Pathway Title	Matching Biomarkers
Pyrimidine metabolism and related diseases (WP4225)	8
Biomarkers for pyrimidine metabolism disorders (WP4584)	7
Urea cycle and associated pathways (WP4595)	6

Diagnosis:
Direction

OTCD is located in Urea cycle

Community-curation of metabolic interactions by experts is needed to support metabolomics data analysis

Rich metabolic interaction annotations are essential to interpret biological mechanisms, particularly for sparse metabolomics datasets

Machine-readable pathway models on Inherited Metabolic Disorders should be used more to support rare disease diagnosis

To know the true identity of a chemical compound in a sample, open source data and a FAIRified annotation workflow should become critical steps in scientific dissemination

Panel discussion - SLIDO

- Go to URL www.slido.com
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Thank you for your time